

Why this cross-country exchange in population health shall be continued

The success of the [Rapid Exchange Forum](#) highlights the importance of collaboration and information exchange in addressing global health challenges. Having a **pre-established network** to exchange information on urgent public health issues is of utmost importance as it can **enable efficient and rapid communication** among relevant stakeholders for both, regular population health topics or present and future crisis in health and care and should therefore be maintained. **Thus**, the Forum can be **used as communication channel for upcoming work** for both, public administration, and research, e.g., defining indicators that need to be monitored for better resilience and preparedness or covering measures to handle Long-COVID.⁵

In order to develop its full potential to support information needs of decision and policy makers it is necessary to **maintain both, the [Health Information Portal](#)** as repository for the evidence and findings generated, **and the REF exchange** as possibility for further mutual learning and capacity building activities, complemented by e.g., a regular European Spring School on Health Information⁶.

To achieve this, the scope of the REF was broadened beyond COVID-19 in December 2022 and some partners, via their competent authorities, reached out to DG SANTE for inclusion of activities in the upcoming **EU4Health Work Programme 2024**.

PROVED VALUE OF THE RAPID EXCHANGE FORUM⁵

- 1 Trust created to share information quickly in a structured and regular manner between 31 European countries.
- 2 Anticipation and identification of upcoming needs of population health issues
- 3 Coverage of a wide breath of existing and emerging topics (see Word cloud)
- 4 Functions as a network of networks with a comprehensive list of experts in different fields. offering quick and reliable information

References

- 1 Habl, C; Röhring, I. (2021): *The PHIRI Rapid Exchange Forum*. European Journal of Public Health, 31 (3), iii154.. ckab164.404. ISSN 1101-1262
- 2 Habl, C; Pries, C. (2022): PHIRI Rapid Exchange Forum (REF): A key tool for cross-country exchange in times of crisis. European Journal of Public Health, 32 (3), iii263. ckac129.646. ISSN 1101-1262
- 3 Tolonen, H; Lapão, L. V; Bogaert, P; Habl, C; Calleja, N. (2023): PHIRI Rapid Exchange Forum (REF): a key tool for cross-country exchange in times of crisis and beyond. Popul. Med. 2023;5 (Supplement), A1615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18332/popmed/165630>.
- 4 For a full list of topics see European Health Information Portal. Rapid Exchange Forum (www.healthinformationportal.eu/rapid-exchange-forum; 05.09.2023)
- 5 Habl, C; Weiss, J; Gottlob, A, Saso, M; Schutte, N; Bogaert, P; Silva P. M; Lapao, L. V; (2023): How to help countries to improve resilience through a pandemic? – Example from a Rapid Exchange Forum. European Journal of Public Health XXXX
- 6 See as latest example the PHIRI Spring School on Health Information 2023 (<https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/activities/spring-school-health-information>)

Disclaimer

The content of this document represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contributors

